

ALCOHOL ACIDITY AS A MEASURE OF SOUNDNESS OF ATA (WHOLE MEAL FLOUR)

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It has already been shown by Mitra¹ that alcohol acidity of flour can be used to determine its condition and also to detect rancidity, particularly at the incipient stage of deterioration. In the present study, the same method has been applied to detect spoilage in ata (whole meal flour), and a maximum permissible limit for alcohol acidity of sound and undamaged ata has been suggested. The earlier suggested standard for flour will not be applicable to ata because the latter contains more fats and oils than the former, and consequently liberates more fatty acids on storage. Also, ata, in general, has more titratable acidity than flour.

EXPERIMENTAL

In order to study how the three acidities, namely, water acidity, alcohol acidity and fat acidity, of ground, whole wheat increase in storage, two fresh samples of wheat (one red and the other a yellow variety) were ground and stored in separate bags in the laboratory. The three acidities were determined at the start, and thereafter at regular intervals until distinct rancidity, as observed by off-flavour and taste, set in after four months of storage.

Samples of ata, in fresh and sound condition, were collected from Calcutta and mofussil markets and were analysed for their acidity contents and moisture. In addition, samples, which were more or less deteriorated and became unsound, were also examined similarly.

Determination of Acidities

The same procedure, as applied to flour², was also followed for ata, i.e. *water extract acidity* was determined by treating 10 g. of sample with 100 ml. of distilled water at room temperature for half an hour, filtering and titrating an aliquot of the clear filtrate with *N/20* caustic soda solution using phenolphthalein as an indicator.

The *alcohol-extract acidity* was determined by treating 5 g. of sample with 50 ml. of 90% neutral alcohol for 24 hours (left overnight), filtering and titrating the entire filtrate with *N/20* alkali.

The *fat acidity* was determined by extracting 10 g. of the sample with petroleum ether for 16 hours in a Soxhlet extractor, evaporating off the solvent, treating the residue with 30 ml. of a neutral 1:1 ethyl alcohol-benzene mixture and titrating with *N/20* alkali.

In all cases results are expressed as "mg. of caustic potash required to neutralise acids in 100 g. of ata", and are on air-dry sample, the moisture content varying from 9 to 10%.

TABLE I
Acidity of sound and deteriorated ata.

		No. of sample.	Water extract acidity.	Alcohol extract acidity.	Fat acidity.
Sound and undamaged ata	Max.	40	190	235	110
	Min.		73	73	28
	Ave.		139	138	73
Deteriorated samples		1.	270	286	—
		2.	160	250	—
		3.	280	286	—
		4.	196	336	—
		5.	280	498	—
		6.	200	252	—
		7.	375	409	—
		8.	235	258	—
		9.*	498	364	—
		10.*	840	420	—
		11.*	560	392	252
		12.*	627	409	221
		13.*	571	381	246
		14.*	644	381	216

These six samples were in the advanced stage of deterioration.

DISCUSSION

Rise, in storage, of acidities of ata, prepared from both red and yellow varieties of wheat, is represented graphically in Figs. 1 and 2

From Figs. 1 and 2, both alcohol and fat acidities appear to increase much more rapidly than the water acidity in the initial stage of the development of rancidity. In the fourth month of storage, i.e. in August, the alcohol acidity in *red* wheat ata has increased by 2.4 times, the fat acidity by nearly 2.6 times, but the water acidity by 1.7 times only. In the *yellow* wheat ata the rise in the corresponding acidities in the same period is by 3.6, 3.8 and 2.6 times respectively. Therefore, at the incipient stage of deterioration,

the alcohol and fat acidities can serve as better indices of spoilage than water acidity, just as for flour. Since the determination of alcohol acidity is far more easy and rapid than that of the fat acidity; the former value can be used conveniently in routine work to determine the "condition" of ata.

FIG. 1
Increase in acidity of red wheat
ata on storage.

FIG. 2
Increase in acidity of yellow wheat
ata on storage.

Curves I—III in Figs. 1 & 2 refer respectively to the water acidity, alcohol acidity and fat acidity.

Results of acidity determination of sound and undamaged ata as also of more or less deteriorated samples are shown in Table I, and the "spread of values" of alcohol acidity in Table II

The significance of the figures of alcohol acidity will be more clear from the "spread of values of alcohol acidity" shown in Table II. It will be seen that 90% of the samples examined gave figures of alcohol acidity ranging from 73 to 185, 7.5% gave figures between 200 and just under 220; and only 2.5% of samples gave figures over 220, which may be considered as a lone, exceptional case. Therefore, for sound ata a value of 220 can be safely accepted as the maximum permissible limit of alcohol acidity, expressed as mg. of caustic potash required to neutralise the acids in 100 g. of material. This limit also fits well with the results of damaged ata shown in Table I, as the alcohol acidities of all the samples exceed 220.

TABLE II*

Spread of values of alcohol acidity of sound ata.

No. of samples examined	14	11	11	3	1
Alcohol acidity	73 to 112	123 to 151	157 to 185	202 to 218	235
All results are on air-dry sample.					(Av. 138)

At the advanced stage of deterioration (samples Nos. 9 to 14 in Table I), the figures for the water acidity are significantly higher than those of the other two acidities for the same reason as given for flour³, but at this stage hardly any chemical test is needed to detect spoilage.

S U M M A R Y

The deterioration of ata on storage, particularly at the incipient stage, can be detected by the determination of the alcohol extract acidity. From the analysis of a large number of samples of sound and undamaged ata, it is suggested that the maximum permissible limit of alcohol acidity (expressed as mg. caustic potash per 100 g. of sample) of sound ata be fixed at 220.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Mitra, S. N., *J & Proc. Inst. Chem., India*, 1952, 24, 138.
2. *Ibid.*, pp. 134—135.
3. *Ibid.*, p. 135.